

Precision Tests of Relativistic Gravity with Advanced Lunar Laser Ranging and Planetary Ephemerides Program

G. Bargiacchi¹, N. Burzillà¹, R. Campagnola¹, S. Dell’Agnello¹, L. Porcelli¹, E. Battista¹, S. Capozziello^{2,3,4}, J. Chabé⁵, J. Chandler^{6,7}, C. Courde⁵, F. Del Ferrero¹, D. Di Serio¹, M. Maiello¹, R. March¹, R. Rodriguez¹, L. Salvatori¹, E. Scantamburlo¹, M. Tibuzzi¹, D. Vetrano¹, B. Villalba¹

1 Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare—Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati (INFN-LNF), Via E. Fermi 54, P.O. Box 13, 00044 Frascati, RM, Italy

2 Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare—Sezione di Napoli (INFN-NA), Via Cintia snc, 80126 Napoli, NA, Italy

3 Scuola Superiore Meridionale, Largo S. Marcellino 10, 80138 Napoli, NA, Italy

4 Dipartimento di Fisica “E. Pancini”, Università di Napoli “Federico II”, Complesso Universitario di Monte S.

Angelo, Via Cinthia snc, Ed. N, 80126 Napoli, NA, Italy

5 Université Côte d’Azur, Observatoire de la Côte d’Azur, CNRS, Laboratoire Géoazur, France

6 University of California, San Diego, 9500 Gilman Drive, La Jolla, CA 92093, USA

7 Center for Astrophysics, Harvard and Smithsonian, 60 Garden Street, Cambridge, MA 02138, USA

Email:

Gbargiacchi@lnf.infn.it	burzilla@lnf.infn.it	roberto.campagnola@lnf.infn.it
Simone.DellAgnello@lnf.infn.it	Luca.Porcelli@lnf.infn.it	emmanuele.battista@lnf.infn.it
salvatore.capozziello@na.infn.it	julien.chabe@geoazur.unice.fr	john.cfa.new@gmail.com
courde@geoazur@unice.fr	deferra@lnf.infn.it	dalila.diserio@lnf.infn.it
Mauro.maiello@lnf.infn.it	riccardo.march@gmail.com	raffaele.rodriquez@lnf.infn.it
lorenzo.salvatori@lnf.infn.it	enrico.scantamburlo@lnf.infn.it	mattia.tibuzzi@lnf.infn.it
dvetrano@lnf.infn.it	blanca.villalba@lnf.infn.it	

Introduction: Lunar Laser Ranging (LLR), i.e., the time-of-flight measurements of short laser pulses fired from ground stations to Laser Retroreflector Arrays (LRAs) of Cube-Corner Retroreflectors (CCRs) on the Moon, has represented since 1969 a benchmark technique for ephemeris information and experimental tests of relativistic gravity in the weak-field, slow-motion regime, providing some of the tightest constraints on General Relativity (GR) [1] and its possible extensions. Decades of continuous improvements in ground-based laser stations have reduced single-shot ranging uncertainties to the millimeter level. However, the overall accuracy of current LLR experiments is now limited by the response of legacy LRAs to lunar librations due to eccentricity and inclination of the Moon orbit [2,3], which dominate the systematic error budget and limit the extraction of relativistic parameters from increasingly precise observations, as for measurements from Apollo (USA) and Lunokhod (USSR) LRAs.

The emergence of a new generation of lunar laser retroreflectors is transforming this experimental landscape [4]. This is the case of Next Generation Lunar Retroreflector (NGLR-1) and Moon Laser Instrumentation for General relativity High-accuracy Tests (MoonLIGHT), which are 100 mm single uncoated CCRs unaffected by lunar librations [2,3,5]. The fixed-pointing NGLR-1 successfully landed on the Moon on Blue Ghost lander built by Firefly Aerospace in March 2025 providing laser returns to the LLR Earth stations at Grasse, Apache Point, and Wettzell. These observations have strongly demonstrated that, compared to LRAs, NGLR-1 provides an

extremely low dispersion of the magnitude of the residuals. The Satellite/lunar/GNSS laser ranging/altimetry and cube/microsat Characterization Facilities Laboratory (SCF_Lab) at the Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare—Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati (INFN-LNF), in collaboration with the University of Maryland (UMD) and supported by the Italian Space Agency (ASI), developed MoonLIGHT that will be launched in November 2026 for the flight NASA-CLPS “CP 11” with Intuitive Machines 3 (IM-3) to the Reiner Gamma swirl [6]. MoonLIGHT is actively oriented through the MoonLIGHT Pointing Actuator (MPAc) instrument, a specifically devised, designed, and manufactured robotic actuator, that will align the front face of MoonLIGHT towards Earth [7], thus allowing a more accurate positioning. MPAc has also been identified by ESA as a mandatory instrument on the payload suite for positioning & navigation Nova-Moon on the first ESA lunar lander ArgoNET [8]. In this scenario, MoonLIGHT (+ MPAc) is designed to deliver short, well-defined laser return pulses, effectively decoupling the ranging observable from lunar libration effects and allowing the intrinsic performance of modern laser stations, and their future improvements, to be fully exploited. Consequently, the improved optical response of next-generation retroreflectors enables a reduction of the retroreflector-induced contribution to the LLR error budget from the centimeter scale toward the millimeter and sub-millimeter regime.

Analyses and simulations on the magnitude of the accuracy improvements from LLR data can be obtained by using the Planetary Ephemeris Program

(PEP) [9,10], a software developed and maintained since the 1960s by the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics (CfA), MA, USA, and currently used by our research group at INFN-LNF. PEP is a software that, among several features, uses LLR data for precision tests of GR and beyond by comparison of GR predictions with observations. Indeed, PEP includes a detailed mathematical model of the solar system with a large set of adjustable parameters, including some that describe fundamental physics. By estimating these parameters, we can restrict the range of allowable theories in physics and cosmology, enabling constraints on departures from standard physics. Notably, PEP constantly keeps improving GR tests and pushes constraints on fundamental physics observables in search of new physics.

In this contribution, we present a physics-driven assessment of the impact of such advances on tests of relativistic gravity using LLR data analyzed with PEP. Indeed, the use of PEP with previous and new more accurate data allows us to improve the accuracy on the constraints of Weak and Strong Equivalence Principles (WEP/SEP), the relative variation with time of the gravitational constant G , and the geodetic precession, and will test departures from GR, enabling studies on new theories beyond GR, like spacetime torsion [11], $f(R)$ gravity [12], nonminimally-coupled gravity [13,14,15], Lorentz-invariance violations, etc. Particular attention is devoted to 1) the processing in PEP of new, recent LLR data, as the laser returns from NGLR-1, 2) the analyses of time-of-flight residuals obtained from LRAs and new generation retroreflectors, 3) the simulation in PEP of dummy data to test how next-generation lunar retroreflectors onboard future missions could improve the accuracy of fundamental physics parameters (see also [16]), 4) the application of PEP to laser ranging between Earth stations and orbiters around the Moon, 5) the estimation of gravitational parameters and their associated accuracy, and 6) the possibility to extend our analyses from Sun-Earth-Moon system to Sun-Earth-Mars system. Regarding this last point, beyond the Earth-Moon system, the extension of laser ranging techniques to planetary surfaces represents a natural and powerful generalization of LLR-based gravity tests. Tests of GR in the Sun-Earth-Mars system will provide complementary constraints on relativistic gravity and extended theories, probing regimes and spatial scales that are not accessible through lunar laser ranging alone.

Summarizing, the combined leverage of next-generation lunar missions, advanced ephemeris, data-analysis tools such as PEP, and future planetary laser-ranging experiments establishes a coherent experimental framework for precision tests of relativistic gravity in the Solar System. This framework tightly integrates fundamental physics with advanced geodesy, metrology, and navigation, and positions laser

ranging as a uniquely cutting-edge powerful tool for exploring subtle relativistic effects and potential signatures of new gravitational physics beyond GR in the puzzling framework of gravitational and cosmological theories.

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